

Oke Isegun (Mountain of Victory)

also known as "Oke Agbara (Power Mountain)"

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Entry tags: Pentecostal Christianity, Sacred mountain, yoruba, Christianity, Religious Group, English, Prayer Mountains in Nigeria, Christ Apostolic Church, Language, Religious Place, Aladura

Oke Isegun (Mountain of Victory) was set up in the year 1931 by the founding General Evangelist of the Christ Apostolic Church Joseph Ayo Babalola. The place has remained a convergence point for members and non-members of the church who seek spiritual interventions to issues they considered overwhelming. The mountain continues to have significant impact on the church members, visitors and the host community of Efon Alaaye and is of great pilgrimage and tourist value. The Christ Apostolic Church (CAC), being a praying church revolutionized the practice of praying among its members significantly by insisting that most problems and challenges met by humans can be addressed by fervent and consistent prayers. In furtherance of this philosophy they needed to dedicate certain spaces considered in their own estimation as sacred for the purpose of supplication and invocation. Joseph Ayo Babalola, who was reputed to be in the habit of praying several hours daily chose the mountain - which was later christened as Oke Isegun - as one of his most preferred prayer venues. Many of his followers claim that the success of Babalola's Christian ministry is, in part attributable to his supplications to and interactions with the supreme being regularly on the mountain. Reports of extraordinary occurrences including healing of all manner of sicknesses and health conditions, deliverance from oppression, gifts of children to the barren, healing of lunatics and others have been made by pilgrims and visitors to the mountain consistently over the years. The mountain is organized such that daily and regular congregational prayers are held there. To sustain the impact of the prayer mountain and keep it in good running order, the place is administered by a committee set up by the leadership of the local parish, Christ Apostolic Church(CAC), Oke Isegun in Efon Alaaye community. The committee takes crucial decisions on the administration of the mountain and keeps the appointed custodian (known as Baba Ori Oke) of the place on a monthly stipend. Since the mountain was set up in 1931 there have been several reports of its spiritual impact on the local population and visitors. It has continued to serve as a spiritual power house to those who believe in its potency while the lives of those who thronged the mountain have been shaped by their concrete faith in the place.

Date Range: 1931 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye community, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

Region tags: South West, North Central and North West Nigeria, Nigeria, Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria., Southwest Nigeria

Oke Isegun, Efon Alaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Photographs taken during participant observation
- Source 2: Oral Interview
- Source 3: Participant Observation

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: <https://www.nairaland.com/5125417/collins-visit-babalolas-tomb-mountain>

– Source 1 Description: Visit to Babalola's Tomb, Mountain and River Oni at Efon Alaaye.

– Source 2 URL:

<https://www.facebook.com/1204689632974771/posts/pfbid02yw299SZSLsf3gM7atzhpd5FScXtSznjMLoMpkuHGVfKVqjTCh4eKSapp=fbl>

– Source 2 Description: Seven of Ayo Babalola Mountain that you need to visit

– Source 3 URL: <https://thetrumpet.ng/symbolic-mountain-top-worship-of-apostle-ayodele-babalola-and-cac/>

– Source 3 Description: Symbolic Mountains top worship of Apostle Ayo Babalola and CAC

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun, Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

Notes: This prayer mountain is of figurative excavation. It is a place that has layers of significance or hidden stories that can be uncovered through investigation or exploration. This means that there is a lot of history or meaning buried beneath the surface. For example the commencement of prayer activities on the mountain is linked to one historical and/or mythological narration or the other. This shows that the choice of the mountain was not arbitrary. The place is associated with one hierophanic occurrence or the other to confirm its sacredness.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun, Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Type of excavation:

– Pre-modern

Notes: It is of figurative excavation

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun, Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Years of excavation:

– Year range: From the time of the establishment of the Prayer Mountain in 1931

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun, Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Name of excavation

– Official or descriptive name: Figurative Excavation

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun, Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Elevation

Notes: The host community is surrounded by hills and mountains. One of these mountains was divinely selected as a suitable place where prayer activities can be established.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun, Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Type of elevation

- Mountain
- Rock face

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun, Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

Notes: There are a number of shelters built to facilitate prayers and other necessary and legitimate activities on the prayer mountain. On the mountain are human-made features like buildings, water borne materials, electricity wiring, mapping out of some spaces considered sacred for special prayer activities.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun, Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Type of feature

- Leveling of ground
- Clearing
- Trackway or road-surface
- Water feature

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun, Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– No

Notes: Although Efon Alaaye community is the most significant community in the Local Government christened after the town, the prayer mountain is not within the central municipality. The natural environmental (features) of the immediate surrounding of the mountain is still being preserved.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun, Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– Yes

Notes: The characteristics of the surrounding area to the prayer mountain depicts those of rural settings. For example, farming activities are noticeable within the precinct of the mountain. The area is not characterised by industrial activities as it also lacks basic social amenities and other infrastructural facilities with which developed societies are known.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun, Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Are there settlements in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun, Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Are there routes of travel in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– Yes

Notes: Non-religious places of habitation are far from the location. The place is located far removed from places of habitation. It is an elevation, a mountain which is higher and far from places of non-religious habitation. Visitors or pilgrims make a pilgrimage to the mountain purposively for spiritual activities, though some structures have been put in place to make the place habitable temporarily for pilgrims or visitors who intend to stay for a while and also for the custodians of the prayer mountain.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Is there an established route of travel connecting it to a wider transportation network:

– Yes

Notes: There are a number of road networks that connect to the prayer mountain. The roads serve as access which facilitate human movement to and from the mountain. The need for vehicular movement has led to the construction of motorable access route. This facilitates human and vehicular movement to and from the mountain and has made the building of so many structures on the mountain possible as carriage of building materials became easier.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

Notes: There are structures built on the mountain for the purpose of facilitating effective prayers for those visiting the place. Structures are put in place for effective religious practices. For example halls for joint prayers, secluded places for personal prayers, guest rooms for visitors who wish to stay long on the mountain, bukateria for purchase of food and food stand for those selling fruits and other snacks. Also enclosurement are built around some sacred spaces to differentiate them from the larger mountain space.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ A single structure

– No

Notes: Many structures are built on the mountain for the purpose of facilitating effective prayers for the visitors.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ One single feature

– Purposefully placed plants

Notes: Some plants are placed to provide shades for visitors and to serve the purpose of wind breakers.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ A group of structures:

– Yes

Notes: The structures on the prayer mountain are made of different designs depending on the intended usage. For example Upper Room Chamber is a storey-building where people gather for special prayer.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun, Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

Notes: They are of different designs made for different purposes.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun, Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ A group of features:

– Yes

Notes: A group of features to serve different purposes.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun, Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

Notes: The features are of different design, some to beautify, some bigger ones to serve as shade under which visitors can enjoy fresh breeze while praying or relaxing, and some to serve as wind breaker. The structures on the prayer mountain are at different construction stages. A few have been built since the establishment of the prayer mountain. Some are recent structures while some are still under construction.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun, Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– Yes

Notes: It is part of a larger space.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun, Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

Notes: The structures and the features are all meant for the purpose of facilitating effective prayers.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun, Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Worship:

– Communal

Notes: It may involve a group of people of common conscience coming together to perform religious ritual. It may also be an individualistic prayer.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

Notes: Some of the structures have been completed while some are still under construction.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

Notes: The intention was for it to last beyond a generation.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

Notes: The old structures were re-shaped and re-built especially the structure put in place on the mountain by the time prayer activities were established on the mountain.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– No

Notes: There has not been any record of destruction since the establishment of prayer activities on the mountain.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– Yes

Notes: Some old structures have been reconstructed to meet the demand of visitors to the prayer mountain.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ In antiquity

– Periodically

Notes: It can be reconstructed at the demand of visitors who are also ready to donate towards the reconstruction. Reconstruction e.g. repainting, re-roofing and renovation of dilapidated buildings are done in preparation for special prayer programmes which holds annually on the prayer mountain.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ In modernity

– Post-Renaissance

Notes: Some of the old structures are being reconstructed.

Specific to this answer:

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: The place is used essentially for Christian prayers to the supreme being. The prayers which are offered on the mountain take the following modes; supplication, intercession, invocation, appeals, etc.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: The prayer mountain is specifically dedicated to God. Those who visit the mountain for prayers hold firmly to the belief that they are there to meet God and to seek His face for favour, blessings, protection, healing etc.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– No

Notes: The prayer mountain is dedicated to God alone. No other power is recognised on the mountain neither is there any form of worship dedicated to another supreme being on this prayer mountain.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Notes: The place is dedicated to the worship of God alone. No other being, either semi-human or angelic (supernatural) is recognised or accorded worship on this mountain. The administrators of the mountain teach that only God is to be looked upon when praying on the mountain.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Notes: Non-divine ancestors are not recognised neither are they worshipped on the mountain.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– No

Notes: The place was built on the meagre resources of the church and the freewill offering of those who visit the mountain for prayers.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Yes

Notes: It is built by the church and the visitors to the prayer mountain.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

Groups:

–Other [specify]: Christ Apostolic Church members, visitors and pilgrims.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– Yes

Notes: The prayer mountain is considered suitable for prayer activities because of its association with one hierophanic or kratophany occurrence or the other that confirmed the sacredness of the place.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

Specify

–Other [specify]: Revealed by manifestation of God's power

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Notes: It is basically a secluded place for effective prayer.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– Yes

Notes: The place was created in obedience to the call of God. Ayo Babalola was said to have been ordered by God to take other pastors and his followers to the mountain to refresh themselves and gain more spiritual power before embarking on any spiritual programme. He was told that the place is a covenant place that has been hidden from people. Since he received the message he has been visiting the mountain, which was then surrounded by a thick forest, whenever he wanted to embark on any spiritual task. The message of God about the mountain was confirmed in 1931 when Ayo Babalola went to pray on the mountain with six(6) of his followers. They all removed their garments and placed them under a tree while they engage themselves in a serious prayers. A heavy downpour started and lasted for the better part of the day, to everybody's amazement the men's garments and books did not get wet. They also discovered that the erosion that was running towards the garments and the books parted ways thereby leaving the garments and books in between two lines of running water. This great occurrence further convinced Ayo Babalola that the place is really a covenant or sacred place.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

Specify

–Other [specify]: Hierophanic Event

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

Is this sponsor of the same religious group/tradition as the main usage of the place:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Thanksgiving to a god/gods for favor received

Notes: The establishment of the place was motivated by thanksgiving to a god for favour received. It was also motivated by the religious experience of Ayo Babalola and his followers during their visit to the mountain.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Notes: It was built as a place of prayers, although altars where scriptures and other sacred literature are kept also form part of the buildings.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

Notes: There are many structures with different designs built on the prayer mountain.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– Yes

Notes: There is a particular structure on the mountain built around a tree. A concrete pavement is constructed around the tree while a barricade is built to encamp the place from other areas on the mountain.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun, Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– No

Notes: No monumental architecture is present on the prayer mountain.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun, Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– No

Notes: They are built out of manufactured products like bricks, concrete nails, concrete, corrugated iron roofing sheets, iron rods, etc. These materials are combined with some natural materials like sand, gravel and stone.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun, Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– Yes [specify]: Blocks, cements, concrete and planks.

Notes: Some of the materials with which the structures are made are human-made materials. Examples are blocks made from cement and other natural materials including sand and water. Other human made materials used in the construction of the buildings include; roofing sheet, iron rods, glass and tiles among others.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun, Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

Notes: The place is adorned with accessories and decoration. The buildings are adorned with ornament and light.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun, Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

Notes: Some of the decorations are part of the buildings and are permanent. A notable example of such permanent decorations is the inscription of biblical passages on the wall. However, some of the decorations are mounted or placed temporarily as they are usually removed at the conclusion of the programme for which they were put in place.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun, Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ On the outside:

– Yes

Notes: Decorations are on the outside of the building.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

Notes: We have both temporary and permanent decoration inside the buildings of the mountain especially the general prayer hall.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– Yes

Notes: For example the prayer hall is always decorated temporarily during general programmes on the mountain and the decoration is removed at the conclusion of the programme.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

Notes: There is an art work that depict the picture of Joseph Ayo Babalola on one of the enclosed sacred spaces on the mountain.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– No

Notes: There are no gods depicted on the prayer mountain.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– No

Notes: There are no other supernatural beings depicted

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– Yes

Notes: No other humans are depicted except a figural painting work of art that depicts the picture of Joseph Ayo Babalola on the prayer mountain.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– No

Notes: There are no animals depicted.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:

– No

Notes: There are no animal-human hybrids depicted.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Yes

Notes: The decoration is non-figural

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Is it geometric/abstract

– Yes

Notes: There are abstract decorations which focus on conveying concepts, emotions and ideas through shapes, colours and forms. For example the work of art that depicts the idea/shape of praying hands of a human being.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Floral motifs

– Yes

Notes: Flowers of different colors are used for decorative purposes. There are the ones that are used for temporary beautification and there are other ones that are permanent, that is, the planted ones.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Is it writing/caligraphy

– Yes

Notes: Inscription of biblical passage on the wall forms part of beautification of some buildings on the mountain.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: Light

Notes: The place is adorned with accessories and decorations. The buildings are beautified with ornaments and light.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

— No

Notes: The decorations are not hidden neither are they restricted from view.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Are there statues present:

— No

Notes: There are no statues present. The church does not support the use of statues.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

— No

Notes: There are no relief sculptures on the buildings of the prayer mountain.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Are there paintings present:

— Yes

Notes: There is figural painting work of art of Joseph Ayo Babalola, the man that established prayer activities on the mountain.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Are they panel paintings [movable]:

— No

Notes: No panel painting is present on the prayer mountain.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Are they wall paintings:

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Type

— Secco

Notes: Secco type of painting is used.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Paintings representing the gods worshipped at the place:

— No

Notes: There are no paintings representing the Supreme High God worshipped on this prayer mountain. Prayers are offered to the supreme God without any image of Him present on the mountain.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Paintings representing mythological narratives:

– No

Notes: No such painting on the prayer mountain.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Paintings representing human/historical narratives:

– Yes

Notes: There is a painting representing the man who established prayer activities on the mountain, Joseph Ayo Babalola. Few of the historical facts about the place is written on a signboard for visitors to view. For example year of establishment, names of the mountain, rules and regulations guiding the use of the prayer mountain.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: Sign-boards

Notes: Sign-boards are erected at every strategic place on the mountain with inscriptions to direct visitors to the right place. For example, the sign-boards direct visitors where to remove their foot-wears, where to place water containers, places that are out of bound to women and some other things one needs to know about the prayer mountain as a visitor are communicated through the sign-boards. The sign-boards bear such inscriptions as "Women should not go beyond this place", "remove your foot-wear here". "drop your offering inside this box" among others. Some of the sign-boards contain pictures that denote these actions.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– No

Notes: There is no mosaics present.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– Yes

Notes: Quotes from the holy book (Bible) are inscribed on the wall on some of the buildings on the prayer mountain.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:

– Yes

Notes: They are ornamental. They add to the beauty of the building.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative
[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]

– Yes

Notes: For example one inscription on The Christ Apostolic church calendars says Jesus is Lord. Another says 'One Fold, one Shepherd'.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:

– No

Notes: They do not denote formal dedication.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Other type of decoration:

–Yes [specify]: Curtain and Linen

Notes: The use of curtain and linen materials to beautify the altar.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– No

Notes: There are no distinct features.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Notes: It is neither a tomb nor burial place. It is a prayer mountain.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Notes: It is not a place for the worship of the dead. Worship of the dead is prohibited by the parent church which oversees the prayer mountain and so worship of the dead is not allowed on the prayer mountain..

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Notes: The prayer mountain was not established to treat corpses.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Notes: The prayer mountain is neither a tomb nor a burial place. Co-sacrifices are therefore not permitted on the prayer mountain.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

Are grave goods present:

– No

Notes: Grave goods are not present on the mountain. There are only consumable goods available for sale to the visitors to the prayer mountain.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

Notes: No cenotaph is mounted or erected on the prayer mountain.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ In cemetery:

– No

Notes: No cemetery on the prayer mountain.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Family tomb/crypt:

– No

Notes: Not usually

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

Domestic context:

Interred beneath floors of house, or in areas of domestic activity

– No

Notes: The place is not meant for the handling and conducting of burial ceremony and there is no funeral rite or ritual required.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

Other

–Other [specify]: Commemoration

Notes: Memorial service is sometimes held in honour and remembrance of Joseph Ayo Babalola, the man who established prayer activities on the mountain.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: God the supreme being is believed to be present there, but not physically or cannot be seen physically. He is believed to be present through some of the spiritual experience of the visitors and pilgrims on the prayer mountain.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

Are they anthropomorphic:

– No

Notes: The presence of the supreme God is only recognized. The supreme God is believed to have some attributes which human beings also share with Him. For example He is believed to possess eyes that can see, ears that can hear, hands that can grasp.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

Are they sky deity:

– No

Notes: He is not a sky deity. He is believed not to be limited to the sky only. He is the supreme God and omnipresent.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

Are they chthonic (underworld)

– No

Notes: He is believed to be the supreme being , the Lord of the celestial or heavenly realms who is opposed to deities or spirit associated to the underworld.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Are they fused with king/kingship role (king = high god)

– Yes

Notes: The church talks a lot about the kingdom of God.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Are they the monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

Notes: The church sees themselves as directly connected to the supreme God. Visitors on the prayer mountain relate directly to God in prayers.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Are they kin relation to elites:

– No

Notes: The supreme God is not limited in his relationship to the elites only.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Are they other type of loyalty or connection to elites:

– No

Notes: No other type of loyalty or connection to elites. The supreme being relate to all in the same way especially those who serve him.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Are they unquestionably good:

– Yes

Notes: The supreme being is unquestionably good.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Are they other:

–Other [specify]: No

Notes: God, the supreme being is believed to be one.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

Notes: It is this divine communication which visitors seek at the mountain that sustains their interest in being on the mountain. Visitors see the mountain as both repository and depository of divine power. It is a sacred place where the divine power of the supreme God is concentrated. It is believed that, there people can connect with the divine and recharge their spiritual energy. People visit the mountain for the reason of tapping into the divine power and feel more connected to the sacred.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Through divination practices:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Through charismatic Leaders on the mountain

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Notes: The church does not believe in the presence of human-spirit

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Notes: Human spirits do not communicate with the living on this mountain. Humans only

communicate with the supreme God here.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Notes: The presence of the supreme God is acknowledged verbally and expressed through actions on the mountain. For example praises, worship, thanksgiving, prayers among others are rendered to the supreme being on the mountain.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Nonhuman spirits can be seen:

– No

Notes: The spirit of the supreme being can not be physically seen but can felt and be manifested through those the spirit possessed. Example of such people are the charismatic religious leaders whose presence on the mountain also attracted people to visiting the prayer mountain.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Nonhuman spirits can be physically felt:

– Yes

Notes: It can be physically felt when God manifests especially in healing miracles. For example a blind person acknowledged that he received his sight through the spirit of the supreme being on the mountain.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

Notes: This communication has built up the interest of visiting the mountain.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

Notes: The communication is continuous.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

Notes: Some charismatic religious leaders on the mountain can interpret dreams.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

Notes: The supreme being communicate in trance possession. Some of the religious leaders fall into trances, receive messages from God to be delivered to visitors on the prayer mountain.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Through divination practices:

– Yes

Notes: Religious leaders on the mountain solve problems of some of the visitors through divination.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– Yes

Notes: Divination on the mountain is strictly through the religious specialist assigned to attend to the spiritual needs of the visitors on the prayer mountain.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

Notes: Religious specialists with divinatory power are responsible for divination on the prayer mountain.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: Also, through charismatic Leaders.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Notes: There are only the presence of human beings on the prayer mountain., though there are maybe some religious specialists that can be described has possessing supernatural power.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Notes: No such communication is recognized at the place.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Notes: The church doesn't support the use of statue to represent any being.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– Yes

Notes: Every activity of the mountain is being monitored spiritually. A group of people has been selected to pray concerning the success of every existing programme on the prayer mountain.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Supernatural monitoring of norm adherence:

– Yes

Notes: Norm adherence is also being monitored spiritually and physically. A selected people pray for and monitor visitors conformity to the established rules and regulations that guides the usage of the prayer mountain.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect offerings:

– No

Notes: The Supernatural being doesn't live on the offerings offered on the mountain but it is believed that supernatural being welcomes offerings and bless those who offer it.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Yes

Notes: Sex is seen as a product of a lifetime commitment between legally married couples. It should not be between the unmarried The prayer mountain often talks about proper sexual conducts of people who visit the place.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Does the worship include sex acts/references:

– No

Notes: It does not include sex acts. Sexual act is prohibited on the prayer mountain.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect proper ritual observance:

– Yes

Notes: Supernatural being care about or expect proper ritual observance. The prayer mountain authority ensure that the people or visitors to the prayer mountain are following the correct religious practices or rituals on the prayer mountain. They also ensure that things are done the right way according to the prayer mountain's religious norms and that the proper ritual are performed correctly.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect performance of rituals:

– Yes

Notes: Prayers are offered daily on the mountain, prayer is seen as an avenue to communicate with the supreme being on all matters bordering on the perfect wellbeing of the people who are associated with the prayer mountain. Other ritual performed on the prayer mountain include fasting and prayer, ritual incubation, ritual bathing, singing, vow making, worship, gift giving rituals, circumambulation of sacred places, among others. All these are established patterned ways of interacting with the supreme being on the prayer mountain.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun, Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect maintenance of the place:

– Yes

Notes: Supernatural being care about the maintenance of the place, the place is well maintained. It is being kept clean always, a register is opened to take daily attendance of visitors or pilgrims to the prayer mountain for security purpose. Social amenities, pipe-borne water and electricity are made available on the prayer mountain, these contribute to the well-being, convenience of the visitors and the pilgrims to the prayer mountain to facilitate effective prayers. There are established rules and regulations, rules of behaviors that guide interactions and expectations on the prayer mountain. Visitor or pilgrims are made to align their actions, attitudes or beliefs with the established norms of the mountain's religious practice. For example women are made to cover their heads, women are not permitted to appear in masculine outfit, male are not permitted to appear in feminine outfit e.g wearing of earring, plaiting of hair by men. Visitors are to follow the instruction given by the spiritual father of the mountain(Baba Ori Oke) father of the mountain. e.g instructions on when to have individual prayer otherwise known as independent prayers and when to gather for communal or general prayers. Baba Ori Oke and other religious specialist or charismatic leaders are expected to be treated with respect. Pilgrims or visitors are to obey rules, laws and adhere to the etiquette of the prayer mountain. Failure to adhere to this norms can lead to rejection or ejection of visitors or pilgrims from the prayer mountain. Old and dilapidated building are renovated

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun, Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect personal hygiene:

– Yes

Notes: Supernatural being expect personal hygiene. The place is kept clean always by volunteers visitors, bathrooms and toilets are built on the prayer mountain

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun, Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Supernatural beings care about honoring oaths:

– Yes

Notes: Visitors make a wish before God with the vow that if the wish comes through he/she will come again to show his gratitude to God through offering or gift such wishes maybe recovery from sickness, getting prosperity, begetting of a child or success on lawsuit, among others.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun, Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Other:

– Other [specify]: He cares about respect for leaders of the place.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun, Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: Visitors communicate with the supreme being directly and also through the spiritual leaders on the prayer mountain who communicate with the supreme being on their behalf.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun, Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

Do visitors communicate with gods:

– No

Notes: Visitors communicate with the supreme being.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun, Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

Do visitors communicate with other supernatural beings:

– No

Notes: Visitors communicate only with the supreme being.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun, Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

Notes: Rituals occur at the prayer mountain, some of the ritual practices are regular events e.g prayers, while some are performed in times of special needs e.g ritual bathing. Rituals that occur on the prayer mountain include, seclusion or spiritual incubation, ritual sleep of healing, preaching, distant prayer, worship, fasting and prayer, dancing, singing, ritual bathing.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun, Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

Do large-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

Notes: This includes large scale prayer meetings at prescribed times of the day./week/year

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun, Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

Notes: This includes personal prayer meetings at one's pleasure and at prescribed times of the day./week/year

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun, Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

– specify: 250-300

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun, Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ How often do these rituals take place:
– specify: Daily, weekly, monthly, annually, quarterly.
Specific to this answer:
Region: Oke Isegun, Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:
– Yes
Notes: Orthodoxy checks are done to ensure that pilgrims or visitors to the prayer mountain hold the correct beliefs or doctrine associated with the establishment of the prayer mountain. This is done through questioning of the visitors or pilgrims by the spiritual leaders of the prayer mountain.
Specific to this answer:
Region: Oke Isegun, Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:
– Yes
Notes: Orthopraxy checks are done to make sure that the visitors or pilgrims are performing the rituals correctly. The visitors or pilgrims are being monitored by the spiritual leaders on the prayer mountain, to ensure that the visitors or pilgrims are following the correct religious practices of the prayer mountain. For example where and when to pray, break fast and how long stay on the prayer mountain.
Specific to this answer:
Region: Oke Isegun, Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Are there synchronic practices:
– Yes
Notes: There are other practices that are diachronic.
Specific to this answer:
Region: Oke Isegun, Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:
– No
Notes: The use of intoxicants are not allowed on the prayer mountain.
Specific to this answer:
Region: Oke Isegun, Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:
– Yes
Notes: Sacrifices of praise are offered on the prayer mountain.
Specific to this answer:
Region: Oke Isegun, Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Are there animal sacrifices:
– No
Notes: Animal sacrifices are not done on the prayer mountain. The church does not support animal sacrifices.
Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Are there human sacrifices:

— No

Notes: Human sacrifices is prohibited on the prayer mountain. The church is against human sacrifices.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Are the sacrificed humans associated in some way:

— No

Notes: No human sacrifice.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

Are there self-sacrifices present:

— No

Notes: No self-sacrifice on the prayer mountain.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

Are material offerings present:

— Yes

Notes: People donate money, tangible and non-tangible materials to the prayer mountain. Amenities like buildings, electric fixtures and others are donated by visitors to the prayer mountain. This has helped in the physical development of the prayer mountain.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Are material offerings mandatory:

— No

Notes: They are not mandatory but visitors are encouraged to give offering of whatever they can afford.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Are material offerings composed of valuable objects:

— Yes

Notes: Valuable items or financial contributions are offered by pilgrims and visitors to the prayer mountain as act of devotion, charity and as expression of gratitude for a prayer wish that comes true. Things that pilgrims and visitors use to donate includes religious text, that is the holy bible and hymn books, blessed oil that is used in religious ceremonies for purification, anointing and spiritual protection. Also furnishing used for worship and prayers for example, altars are also donated. Religious art and décor like paintings or decorative items depicting religious theme are also donated.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Are material offerings composed of daily-life objects:

– Yes

Notes: Material offered composed of daily-life object such as buckets, brooms, bowls, mattress among others.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches):

– No

Notes: Material offerings are not interred on the prayer mountain.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Material offerings can be building materials or any other household materials needed in the place.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– Yes

Notes: It is mandatory for visitors and pilgrims to attend to worship on the prayer mountain. Worship, on the mountain, entails expression of reverence, devotion and adoration towards the supreme being. It involves prayer, reading of sacred text and preaching, singing and dancing to praise, glorify or invoke the supreme being, and other rituals on the prayer mountain. The songs are invocative and spontaneous and are usually accompanied with musical instrument, with clapping and movement of the body and raising of arms along with shouting of hallelujah. Much importance is given to singing and dancing during worship on the prayer mountain.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ By all the community

– Yes

Notes: Expect those days that are set aside for independent worship.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ By specific individuals

– Yes [specify]: Those who are set aside for special prayers.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

Notes: Maintenance is performed by selected group of people and volunteers.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Is it required:

– Yes

Notes: Pilgrims and visitors are encouraged to take care of the prayer mountain and to obey the rules and regulation that guide the upkeep of the prayer mountain.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– No

Notes: No cleansing is required from the prayer mountain.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– Yes

– Yes

Notes: Repairs of electrical fixtures and other amenities. Reconstructions of dilapidated and old buildings, roads among others.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– Yes

Notes: It is performed by the church authority and the committee set up to see to the upkeep of the mountain through the spiritual father(Baba Ori Oke) of the mountain.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: At times, the maintenance, especially the cleaning of the place may be done or is done by volunteers among the visitors or pilgrims.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

Notes: Visitors travel from far and near to visit the prayer mountain.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:

–optional (common)

–optional (common)

–obligatory for some

–obligatory for some

Notes: Pilgrims from different walks of life visit the mountain on their own. They see the prayer mountain as being significant for their spiritual, social, psychological and economic value. The prayer mountain is believed to be a devotional center for anyone seeking divine inspiration and intervention. For example those who are looking for job, success in

examination, success in lawsuit and business transactions. These set of people resort to visionary and revelational experience by visiting the sacred mountain in the hope of getting spiritual solution to their problems. Political elites, business men and women visit the prayer mountain to seek the help of the spiritual and charismatic leaders for power and spiritual mandate for their political ambitions and business affair. Pilgrimage to the mountain is obligatory for some especially members of Christ Apostolic Church (CAC) who are mandated to visit the mountain at a particular period of time. The spiritual leaders visit the mountain for spiritual rejuvenation especially when they want to embark on a spiritual task. Also, some misbehaved religious specialist (especially of the Christ Apostolic Church faith) who might have been suspended by the church are mandated to climb the prayer mountain (maybe as punitive measure) to stay there for specific days for fasting and prayers after which they are considered to be capable of being restored.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun, Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Are pilgrimages the main reason for construction/establishment of the place:

– No

Notes: Initially the place was not established for pilgrimages. The prayer mountain is a secluded place where one can fellowship with God with less distraction. Those who visit the place believe they are able to receive power to renew their divine strength. It is believed that visiting the prayer mountain and the participation in the rituals which are associated with religiously significant events that occurred during the life time Ayo Babalola could bring the reoccurrence of the past. This mountain having been considered sacred is now being visited by members of the church and visitors or pilgrims from different walks of life everyday. The mountain has, as a result turned to a tourist and pilgrimage centre.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun, Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Are pilgrimages to this place associated with significant life events:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun, Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Does pilgrimage to this place involve following established routes (roads):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun, Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Are these routes maintained together with the place:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun, Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– No

Notes: The prayer mountain is not a place for feasting, it is strictly a place for prayers.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun, Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

Are festivals present:

– No

Notes: Festivals are not held on the prayer mountain.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun, Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

— Yes

Notes: Though, personal encounter with the supreme being is emphasized on the prayer mountain, visitors or pilgrims contact the spiritual father on the prayer mountain for personal prayers and counselling and to seek guidance, understanding or clarity about the unknown aspects of their lives. It is believed that the spiritual leaders on the prayer mountain are endowed with great prayer power and authority so when peoples problem reach certain inexplicable dimension they believe that some evil powers are at work and they need the help of the spiritual leader who could counter the evil force.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun, Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Divination by examination of the exta:

Animals remains, internal organs, answer this question and subsequent question once for each species

— No

Notes: Divination by examination of the sacred book.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun, Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Divination through human communication:

— Yes

Notes: Divination is done through the spiritual father, and other spiritual leaders of the prayer mountain.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun, Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Is a human being the vehicle for the oracle:

— Yes

Notes: The spiritual father (Baba Ori Oke) of the prayer mountain and other spiritual leaders in charge of the prayer mountain are the ones conveying the message of the supreme being concerning any guidance the visitors or pilgrims seek about the unknown aspect of their lives.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun, Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Is a human being the interpreter of the oracle:

— Yes

Notes: The oracle is being interpreted by the spiritual leaders of the prayer mountain.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun, Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Are the oracle interpreters of a specified sex/gender:

— Yes

Notes: The oracle interpreter are all males. The administrative structure of the prayer

mountain does not allow for active participation of females.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Are the oracle interpreters of a specified ethnicity:

– No

Notes: The oracle interpreters are of diverse ethnicity, but of the same Christ Apostolic Church (CAC) faith.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Are the oracle interpreters of a specified class:

– Yes

Notes: The oracle interpreters are all of the same class of religious specialist.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Is sex-deprivation required:

– Yes

Notes: Sex-deprivation is required especially during fasting and prayers on the prayer mountain.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Are intoxicants required:

– No

Notes: The use of intoxicants are not allowed on the prayer mountain.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Physical ordeal required:

– No

Notes: Physical ordeal is not required.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Divination through animal-behavior:

– No

Notes: Only divination through human being is present.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Divination through non-living material:

–Other [specify in comments]

Notes: Divination is not through non-living material.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Divination

Notes: Divination through prophesy, vision, trance and dreams.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– Yes

Notes: Healing is present. Visitors or pilgrims are miraculously healed of their illnesses, which is one of the reason pilgrims are visiting the prayer mountain.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Incubation

– Yes

Notes: Some of the visitors or pilgrims spend days on the prayer mountain for spiritual incubation. Some pilgrims or visitors claimed that they have come to the mountain to stay away from activities and people to give more time to prayers, for a while possibly until their problems are solved.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Healing magic

– No

Notes: The prayer mountain does not support magic.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Cleansing

– Yes

Notes: Cleansing is done through cold bath, the sanctified water used in cleansing is not to be heated and should not be used with any other drug so as to bring desire result.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Offerings of models of body parts:

– No

Notes: No use of statue or representation of body parts.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Expiation

– Yes

Notes: Expiation is done in confession of sins committed and forgiveness prayers.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Other

—Other [specify]: Olive oil and water may be anointed for use on the mountain or for visitor's use at their residence when they descend from the mountain.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

— Yes

Notes: The church chooses religious specialists who are in charge of the prayer mountain. They are known as Baba Orioke (spiritual father of the mountain) and are being paid a monthly stipend for being in charge of the place. The spiritual fathers (Baba Orioke) are fully in charge of the prayer mountain. They live there, they have their own apartment out of the buildings on the prayer mountain, though they may be invited for another prayer programme elsewhere at times.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

Present full time

— Yes

Notes: They are present full time.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

Present part time

— Yes

Notes: Some spiritual specialists are present on this mountain part time.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

— Yes

Notes: The assigned leader of the mountain is usually a male. He may be supported by male or female religious professionals in administering the mountain. Females are not allowed to serve as a leader on the prayer mountain, there are spaces on the prayer mountain considered sacred and are out of bound to females.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

— No

Notes: The religious leaders are drawn from different ethnicity once they are of Christ Apostolic Church (CAC) faith.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

— No

Notes: The religious leaders are of different classes. They only need to meet the spiritual expectations before they can be chosen as the spiritual father (Baba Orioke) of the prayer mountain.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun, Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

— No

Notes: Religious specialists are not dedicated to the prayer mountain for life. They can move or be transferred to another place of assignment by the church. They themselves can decide to leave the prayer mountain for another place.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun, Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:

— Yes

Notes: There are the senior spiritual leaders and the junior spiritual leaders according to their year of service.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun, Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy:

— Yes

Notes: The senior spiritual father (Baba Orioke) is fully in charge of the affairs of the prayer mountain while others are subject to him.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun, Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

— Yes

Notes: The religious specialists are allocated different apartment.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun, Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

— Yes

Notes: The prayer mountain is used for the spiritual training of religious specialist. At times they come there for spiritual rejuvenation and especially when about to embark on spiritual task.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun, Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

— Yes

Notes: The prayer mountain is being maintained by a committee set up by Christ Apostolic Church (CAC) Oke Isegun, Efon Alaaye. The committee is responsible for the running of event on the prayer mountain, selection of the spiritual father (Baba Orioke) of the mountain, his remuneration and taking of disciplinary measure against him if he errs.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– Yes

Notes: There are rules and regulations guiding visitors and pilgrims activities on the prayer mountain. For example the first thing a visitor or a pilgrim has to do on getting to the prayer mountain is to register his/her name.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Is a bureaucracy present permanently:

– Yes

Notes: The rules and regulations are permanent. Some have been inscribed on the notice board for the attention of visitors and pilgrims. The spiritual father (Baba Orioke) ensures that visitors and pilgrims conform to these rules, regulations and procedures associated with the establishment of the prayer mountain.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Is a bureaucracy present on a temporary or seasonal basis:

– No

Notes: Bureaucracy is present on a permanent basis.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– Yes

Notes: The prayer mountain controls land resources.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Is this control the primary supporting income of this place:

– Yes

Notes: Buildings are erected on the available land for easy accommodation of the pilgrims who are made to pay a token for the accommodation.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Does this place lease out land:

– No

Notes: The place do not lease out land.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Does this place lease out tools:

– No

Notes: The place does not lease out tools. The religious tool used on the prayer mountain are the symbolic objects said to have been handed over to Ayo Babalola by God to use in his ministry. They are water, oil, bell, the holy bible.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun, Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– Yes

Notes: The prayer mountain serves as a location for services to the host community. Some visitors to the prayer mountain are not there for pilgrimage. Their visitation to the prayer mountain is purely economic. They come to sell items like water bottles, kegs which pilgrims use to fetch holy water. Bottles for oil of consecration. They sell other things like foot wears, Christian literature books and food items. Some are there as bike riders to convey pilgrims to and fro the prayer mountain. Thus, the prayer mountain is significant for its economic values. The prayer mountain has brought physical development to the community where it is located. For example guest houses are built in the community for visitors to lodge in. The presence of the prayer mountain affect the population of the community as more people have come to settle temporarily or permanently in the community and traders have more people to buy their wares. The prayer mountain brings oneness, brotherhood, togetherness and fellowship. No matter the pilgrims differences, they are bounded together by the same religious and ethical codes of the mountain.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun, Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Public food distribution and/or storage:

– No

Notes: No provision for public food distribution and food storage on the prayer mountain.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun, Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Place for civic functions (census, elections, others):

– No

Notes: No place for civic functions on the prayer mountain.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun, Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Place for the practice of justice (trials, executions, etc.):

– No

Notes: The prayer mountain is strictly meant for spiritual activities.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun, Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Function for water management:

– No

Notes: The prayer mountain does not function for water management.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun, Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Part of the transportation network:

— No

Notes: The prayer mountain is not part of the transportation network.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Other

—Other [specify]: A place of seclusion.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

— No

Notes: Non-religious writing are not stored in the place. The holy book (Bible) and other Christian literature books are being stored in the place.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

— Yes

Notes: The concept of sacred mountain appears in all the scriptures of the bible except in Ruth, Ecclesiastes, Esther and Ezra. For example Moses received a sacred instruction on mount Sinai, mount Zion is the sight of the temple. There was an establishment of the covenant on mount Sinai. Mount Sinai is a sacred mountain on which according to Exodus 19 the Hebrew prophet and law giver Moses, received from Yahweh the tablets of the ten commandment mount Sinai was regarded as a sacred mountain (Deut33:2, Judges 5:5). These mountains mentioned in the bible are believed to have special spiritual qualities that set them apart from ordinary localities. Christ Apostolic Church(CAC) conception of mountain as a sacred place where one can meet with God has its basis in the bible. The church often refer to some verses in the bible to justify the practice of visiting prayer mountain. examples of bible verses that make reference to praying on the mountain such as 1 kings 18:20-42, psalm 68:6, 2 Sam 15:32, Matt 17:1-13 and so on, where references are made to Moses, Elijah and Jesus all having intercession or sojourned on mountains.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Are they written:

— Yes

Notes: The scriptures are written.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Are they written at this place:

— No

Notes: They are documented in the Bible.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Are they oral:

– No

Notes: They are written.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Is there a story associated with the origin and/or construction of this place:

– Yes

Notes: The mountain was established as a prayer mountain in 1931 by Joseph Ayo Babalola. He established prayer activities on the mountain in obedience to the call of God and being convinced by the hierophanic occurrence on the mountain which confirmed the sacredness of the place.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Are there religious specialists in charge of interpreting the scriptures:

– Yes

Notes: There are religious specialists in charge of the prayer mountain. They interpret the scriptures.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

↳ Are the scriptures part of the building/place:

– No

Notes: The scriptures are not part of the building. The scriptures are documented in the holy book, the Bible.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Oke Isegun,Efon Alaaye, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

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